

Subanesthetic Ketamine Alters EEG Signal Complexity: Implications for Treatment Stratification in Depression

Weng-Lam Chan^a, Sebastian Olbrich^b, Xinwen Jiang^a, Haoyun Zhang^a, Cheng-Teng Ip^{a**†}, Martin Brunovsky^{c,d†}

Affiliations:

^a Centre for Cognitive and Brain Sciences, University of Macau, Taipa, Macau SAR, China

^b Hospital for Psychiatry, Psychotherapy and Psychosomatic; University Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

^c National Institute of Mental Health, Klecany, Czech Republic

^d Charles University, Third Faculty of Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

Word count abstract: 241 (250)

Word count text: 3984 (5000)

Figures: 4

Tables: 2

Supplementary materials: 1

* Correspondence to: Cheng Teng Ip

Centre for Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Research Building N21

University of Macau, Avenida da Universidade

Taipa, Macau SAR

Tel: +853 8822 9378

E-mail: chengtengip@um.edu.mo

[†] Cheng Teng Ip and Martin Brunovsky contributed equally as last authors.

Abstract

Major depressive disorder, particularly its treatment-resistant form (TRD), poses significant treatment challenges. Ketamine, an N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor antagonist, has shown promise in rapidly alleviating depressive symptoms by influencing neuroplasticity and glutamatergic modulation, which are thought to influence brain activity complexity. In this placebo-controlled study, we examined the effects of subanesthetic doses of intravenous ketamine on EEG signal complexity in 24 MDD patients, 21 of whom had TRD. Treatment response was defined by a $\geq 33\%$ reduction in Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) after ketamine administration. Patients underwent eyes-closed resting state EEG recording pre-, start-, end- and 24h post-infusion, analyzed for temporo-spatial and spatiotemporal Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZC_T and LZC_S). Results indicated that ketamine significantly increased whole-brain LZC_T during infusion compared to placebo (sodium chloride 0.9%) (16.90% vs. -4.84%, 95% CI 4.29 to 39.18, $p = 0.017$). Elevated LZC_T at end-pre was associated with less short-term symptom improvement the following day. Conversely, lower pretreatment occipital LZC_T (0.33 vs. 0.46, 95% CI 0.007 to 0.26, $p = 0.040$) predicted a favorable response to ketamine, supported by a logistic regression model with an ROC area of 0.75. No significant changes were observed in LZC_S , suggesting limited utility as a biomarker. In conclusion, occipital LZC_T could serve as an effective predictive biomarker for ketamine's therapeutic effects in MDD, with implications for patients with TRD. This underscores the potential of EEG complexity measures in stratifying treatment and enhancing our understanding of the neural impacts of ketamine in depressive disorders.

Keywords

MDD, ketamine, EEG, biomarker, Lempel-Ziv complexity, treatment response

1. Introduction

Major depressive disorder (MDD) is a pervasive and debilitating mental health condition, with its treatment-resistant form (TRD) posing significant clinical challenges. TRD is defined by a lack of response to at least two distinct antidepressants (McIntyre et al., 2023), such as monoamine reuptake inhibitors, and affects approximately 30% of patients with depression. TRD underscores the need for more effective therapeutic options (Ionescu et al., 2015; McIntyre et al., 2023). Among emerging treatments, ketamine—a glutamatergic antagonist originally developed as an anesthetic (Gonda et al., 2023; Krystal et al., 2013)—has shown promise for patients unresponsive to standard therapies, demonstrating rapid antidepressant effects through mechanisms distinct from conventional therapies (Marcantoni et al., 2020; McIntyre et al., 2020; Sos et al., 2013; Zhou et al., 2022).

Ketamine's antidepressant effects are thought to be mediated by its ability to enhance neuroplasticity and modulate glutamatergic transmission (Abdallah et al., 2018; Aleksandrova and Phillips, 2021). This process involves the upregulation of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and activation of the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathways, which are crucial for improving frontal network connectivity (Deyama and Kaneda, 2023; Zhou et al., 2014). Deficits in balance between excitation/inhibition (E/I) in cortical circuits, a hallmark of TRD, can disrupt frontal network function, contributing to cognitive and affective symptoms (Aleksandrova and Phillips, 2021; López-Solà et al., 2020; Xue et al., 2017). Supporting these mechanistic insights, neuroimaging studies provide evidence of ketamine's impact on brain function. For instance, with diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) technique, research has revealed microstructural neuroplasticity in critical brain regions like the prefrontal cortex, left amygdala, and hippocampus within 24 hours post-infusion, correlating with better clinical improvements

(Kopelman et al., 2023). Similarly, functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) studies have shown increased functional connectivity in prefrontal and limbic regions after ketamine administration, associated with better treatment responses (Rengasamy et al., 2024). Biomarkers studies further support these findings, highlighting changes in functional connectivity (Salvadore et al., 2010), white matter integrity (Vasavada et al., 2016), and gamma power (Nugent et al., 2019), all of which enhance our understanding of ketamine's therapeutic potential.

Electroencephalography (EEG) has emerged as a crucial tool in capturing these dynamic brain changes induced by ketamine. Ketamine has also been shown to reduce EEG vigilance, marked by an increase in stage B1 during infusion, reflecting decreased wakefulness and enhanced fast oscillations (Ip et al., 2024). Beyond these biomarkers, EEG neural complexity, particularly Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZC), offers a promising biomarker closely linked with the integrity of inter-neuronal connectivity (Lempel and Ziv, 1976; Murphy et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2015). LZC, an algorithmic measure of neural signal complexity, is particularly well-suited for capturing ketamine-induced changes in brain activity due to its sensitivity to dynamic oscillatory systems (Aboy et al., 2006; Lempel and Ziv, 1976; Zhang et al., 2013). Research has shown that LZC is altered in conditions like unipolar depression are associated with increased LZC, particularly in the frontal region due to impaired cortical inhibition and reduced network efficiency (Bachmann et al., 2015; Hernández et al., 2023; Mohammadi and Moradi, 2021). Ketamine, by enhancing excitatory activity and promoting neuroplasticity, has been shown to elevate LZC shortly after administration in healthy individuals, correlating with subjective psychedelic experiences such as sensory alteration and dissociation (Farnes et al., 2020; Schartner et al., 2017). In late-life TRD, a recent study found that LZC significantly increased after ketamine infusion, but this enhancement did not persist in the following days (Murphy et

al., 2023). These findings suggest that LZC could serve as a potential biomarker for assessing the therapeutic effects of ketamine and the neural mechanisms underlying treatment response.

Despite its promise, the specific relationship between LZC and the regional network's functional dynamics, particularly the frontal network, remains underexplored. Frontal circuits are central to cognitive and emotional regulation, and their dysfunction in MDD is well-documented (Arns et al., 2017; Fitzgerald et al., 2008; Ip et al., 2021b). However, whether LZC changes in the frontal region specifically correlate with symptom improvement or treatment resistance remains unclear. Furthermore, the utility of LZC in predicting treatment response to ketamine, particularly in TRD, has not been systematically validated. By leveraging a placebo-controlled design (Sos et al., 2013), this study provides a robust framework for isolating ketamine-specific effects on LZC, enabling a more precise evaluation of its therapeutic potential. In this secondary analysis of our previously reported clinical trial (Meyer et al., 2021), we aim to investigate the rapid and residual effects of ketamine on both temporospatial and spatiotemporal measures of LZC, which refer to time dynamics and global changes among electrodes respectively (Li and Mashour, 2019; Murphy et al., 2023). We hypothesized that ketamine increases LZC during infusion, reflecting enhanced cortical dynamics and that regional variations may serve as predictive biomarkers for treatment response. Additionally, we explore whether LZC correlates with symptom severity, offering further insights into its potential role in stratifying patients for ketamine therapy.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Patients

Detailed methodologies and participant recruitment processes were described elsewhere (Ip et al., 2024; Meyer et al., 2021). Twenty-four patients aged 18 to 65, diagnosed with MDD

according to DSM-IV criteria and confirmed through the Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview. Recruitment occurred between 2010 and 2015 (EudraCT Number: 2013-000952-17). Key inclusion criteria included a Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) score of 20 or higher and a history of non-response to at least one adequate antidepressant treatment, with 21 classified as having TRD. All participants were required to maintain stable antidepressant dosages for at least four weeks prior to enrollment, with no treatment augmentation permitted. Exclusion criteria included suicide risk, current psychiatric comorbidities, and serious unstable medical or neurological conditions. See supplement materials S.1 for the study flow diagram.

2.2. Study design and procedures

The study employed a controlled single-blind, one-arm, fixed-sequence design without randomization. Participants first received a placebo infusion, followed by ketamine infusion after a 7-day washout period. Care providers and evaluators were aware of the infusion sequence. All participants provided informed consent. All data were anonymized. The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Prague Psychiatric Centre/National Institute of Mental Health and followed the Declaration of Helsinki's ethical standards.

2.3. Ketamine and placebo infusion

Infusions were administered via a unilateral intravenous catheter placed in the participants' forearms, using an infusion pump (ID 20/50, Polymed Medical CZ Ltd). For the ketamine infusion, participants received a total dose of 0.54 mg/kg racemic ketamine hydrochloride (Calypsol, Gedeon Richter Plc., Czech Republic) over 30 minutes, consisting of a loading dose of 0.27 mg/kg followed by a maintenance infusion of 0.27 mg/kg over 20 minutes. In the placebo

infusion, participants received an equivalent volume of saline solution (0.9% sodium chloride), administered in the same manner.

2.4. Clinical measures and treatment response

Serum samples for ketamine and norketamine levels were collected at 10 and 30 minutes following the first loading dose of ketamine. Depressive symptom severity was assessed using the MADRS at pretreatment (pre-infusion), 24 hours, 4 days, 7 days and 14 days post-infusion. A treatment response was defined as a decrease of more than 33% in MADRS scores measured 24 hours after infusion. This criterion was also used in prior studies involving the same cohort to allow for the inclusion of more responders (Ip et al., 2024; Meyer et al., 2021).

2.5. EEG recordings and processing

EEG recordings were conducted using a 22-channel BrainScope digital amplifier (M&I, Prague, Czech Republic), following the extended international 10-20 system. Participants were seated semi-recumbently with eyes closed in a sound-attenuated room. EEG data were sampled at 1000 Hz, with impedances maintained below 5 k Ω . EEG recordings were taken at baseline (pre-infusion), 10 minutes after the first infusion (start-infusion), and 20 minutes after the second infusion (end-infusion) to capture rapid effects. An additional 10-minute recording was conducted 24 hours post-infusion to evaluate any residual effects. Data preprocessing involved re-referenced to an average reference, and manual removal of artifacts such as sudden movements and impedance-related issues using DeepPsy software. Independent component analysis (ICA) was employed to correct eye movement, cardioballistic effects, and technical disturbances. No significant differences were observed in the exclusion of epochs and ICAs across conditions; further details can be found in Ip et al. (2024). A bandpass filter (0.5–70 Hz)

and a 50 Hz notch filter were applied, with bad channels reconstructed using spherical spline interpolation (Perrin et al., 1987).

2.6. Lempel-Ziv complexity of EEG signal

Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZC) analysis was performed to evaluate the EEG signal's complexity, indicating the richness of neuronal connectivity (Lempel and Ziv, 1976). LZC was computed from the first 10 minutes of the end-infusion recordings for consistency across all treatment conditions. Following the calculation described in a previous study (Aamodt et al., 2023), preprocessed EEG signals were downsampled to 250 Hz, and a Hilbert transform was applied to extract instantaneous amplitude before binarization based on the median value. The algorithm quantified randomness by counting unique binary patterns, expressed as “0”s and “1”s. Analysis included both temporospatial (LZC_T) and spatiotemporal (LZC_S) complexity indices (Li and Mashour, 2019). LZC_T assessed distinct temporal patterns across channels, normalized against a randomly shuffled baseline to provide values ranging from 0 (uniform) to 1 (max randomness) (Casali et al., 2013). The LZC_T was analyzed at whole-brain and regional levels, averaging values across all electrodes or specific regions: frontal (Fp1, Fp2, AFz, F3, F4, F7, F8, Fz), parietal (P3, P4, Pz, C3, C4, Cz), temporal (T3, T4, T5, T6), and occipital (O1, O2). In contrast, LZC_S focused on spatial patterns variability at each time point (Casali et al., 2013), and was evaluated in one-minute blocks to detail temporal variations, as well as over the entire 10 minutes segment to assess broader changes.

2.7. Statistical analyses

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 27.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) and RStudio 2024.4.1.748 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). Repeated measures ANOVA was employed to examine the rapid and sustained effects of ketamine on

LZC, as well as the predictive value of baseline LZC. Age and gender were included as covariates in all models, following previous analyses (Lord and Allen, 2023; Méndez et al., 2012). Degrees of freedom were adjusted using the Greenhouse-Geisser correction when necessary, and Bonferroni's correction was applied for multiple comparisons and post hoc analyses to control for Type I errors. Partial correlations, also adjusted for age and gender, explored the relationships between LZC and clinical measures. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Detailed statistical methods were organized into the following three parts:

2.7.1. Rapid and remaining effects of ketamine on LZC

The effects of ketamine on LZC were assessed by comparing EEG data from ketamine and placebo infusions. Relative LZC changes at start-infusion, end-infusion and 24 hours post-infusion were calculated as the difference from pre-infusion, normalized to pre-infusion measurements (start-pre, end-pre and 24h-pre). For rapid effect analysis in both LZC_T and LZC_S indices, intervention (ketamine vs. placebo) and treatment condition (start-pre vs. end-pre) were included as within-subject factors, while group (responders vs. non-responders) was included as a between-subject factor. Regional LZC_T analyses included brain region (frontal, parietal, temporal, occipital) as additional within-subject factor, while in 1-min block analysis of LZC_S, recording block was included (1min, 2min, ..., 10min) as a within-subject factor. The model analyzing remaining effect retained all factors from the rapid effect model except treatment condition, focusing only on LZC changes from 24 hours onwards (24h-pre). Partial correlations, adjusted for age and gender, were performed to explore the relationships between LZC and clinical measures, specifically how changes in LZC during infusion correlated with serum levels of ketamine and norketamine.

2.7.2. Pretreatment LZC as predictive biomarker for ketamine response

Pretreatment LZC value was tested as a predictive biomarker in an ANOVA model to determine its utility in predicting ketamine response. The predictive value of pretreatment LZC was further assessed using a logistic regression model without regularization, from which the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve was derived.

2.7.3. Association between LZC and MADRS scores

This analysis aimed to investigate the association between the complexity of neural patterns (at pretreatment and changes during infusion) and the severity of depressive symptoms (at pretreatment and subsequent symptom improvement in the days following ketamine treatment). To further explore the nuanced association between pretreatment LZC and symptom severity across responders and non-responders, we conducted partial correlations for pretreatment LZC and MADRS scores at pre-infusion and 24 hours post-infusion, which is the timepoint at which responders and non-responders were defined. For the analysis of LZC and MADRS scores at pre-infusion, we pooled measurements from both the ketamine and placebo interventions to increase the sample size.

3. Results

3.1. Patient demographics

The demographic results were reported in our previous publication (Ip et al., 2024). In brief, 12 patients were classified as responders and 12 as non-responders to ketamine treatment, with no significant differences in age, gender, or pretreatment MADRS scores between the groups (p values > 0.052 , Table 1).

3.2. Rapid ketamine effects on LZC during infusion

The whole-brain model on LZC_T showed a significant intervention effect ($F(1,20) = 9.36, p = 0.006$), such that ketamine induced a greater changes in LZC_T compared to placebo (16.90% vs. -4.84%, 95% CI [4.29, 39.18], $p = 0.015$, Figure 1). The three-way interaction between intervention, conditions, and group was not significant ($F(1,20) = 0.001, p = 0.97$), suggesting that the observed effect of ketamine on LZC_T was consistent across both responders and non-responders. However, no significant partial correlation was observed between the percentage changes in LZC_T at start-pre or end-pre and the levels of serum ketamine or norketamine (p values > 0.15). The regional analyses of LZC_T did not yield significant differences across brain regions (p values > 0.23), indicating that ketamine's rapid effects on LZC_T were not region-specific. The analyses on LZC_S analyses did not reveal any significant effects (p values > 0.26).

3.3 Pretreatment LZC as predictive biomarker for treatment response

No significant results were found in the whole-brain LZC_T analyses (p values > 0.052). The regional LZC_T analysis revealed a significant interaction between brain region, intervention and group ($F(3,60) = 4.21, p = 0.035$), showing that responders exhibited lower occipital LZC_T values than non-responders before ketamine administration (0.33 vs. 0.46, 95% CI [0.007, 0.26], $p = 0.040$, Figure 2A). However, no significant difference was observed in frontal LZC_T values between group (0.40 vs. 0.41, 95% CI [-0.11, 0.11], $p = 0.96$, Figure 2A). The LZC_S analyses did not yield any significant result (p values > 0.32). Occipital LZC_T values were employed as predictive markers for treatment response within a logistic regression model. The analysis revealed a 50% response rate at an occipital LZC_T threshold of 0.39, and achieved an accuracy of 71%, with the optimal cutoff distinguishing responders and non-responders at an occipital LZC_T threshold of 0.5 (S.2). This model yielded a recall of 0.75, precision of 0.69, and a ROC-AUC of 0.75 (Figure 2B).

3.4. Association between LZC and clinical depressive scores

In all patients, a negative partial correlation was observed between end-pre LZC_T changes and 24-hour MADRS improvement ($r(20) = -0.43, p = 0.038$, Table 2, Figure 3), suggesting that greater increase in LZC_T was associated with less short-term symptom improvement. No significant correlation was found between whole-brain LZC_T at other treatment conditions and MADRS scores at other timepoints (p values > 0.15 , Table 2). As no region-specific ketamine effect was found, the association with regional LZC_T was not investigated. In non-responders specifically, only pretreatment frontal LZC_T was found significantly correlated with pretreatment MADRS scores ($r(20) = 0.41, p = 0.049$, Table 2, Figure 4A). In contrast, pretreatment whole-brain ($r(8) = 0.69, p = 0.012$), frontal ($r(8) = 0.66, p = 0.021$), temporal ($r(8) = 0.73, p = 0.0067$) and occipital ($r(8) = 0.83, p < 0.001$). LZC_T were positively correlated with MADRS score changes at 24h post-ketamine infusion in responders (Table 2, Figure 4B), but not in non-responders (p values > 0.57). No significant correlation was found in LZC_S (p values > 0.096).

3.5. Remaining ketamine effects on LZC 24h post-infusion

The whole-brain model of LZC_T did not show any significant results (p values > 0.50). Neither the regional analyses of LZC_T nor LZC_S showed any significant findings (p values > 0.15).

4. Discussion

This placebo-controlled study investigated the effects of subanesthetic doses of ketamine on EEG signal complexity in patients with MDD, focusing particularly on those with TRD. By using Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZC), we assessed both temporospatial (LZC_T) and spatiotemporal (LZC_S) complexity measures to evaluate changes in brain activity over time and across different brain regions. Our primary findings indicate that ketamine significantly elevated

whole-brain LZC_T during infusion compared to placebo, suggesting an enhancement in neuronal activity and complexity. Interestingly, elevated LZC_T at the end of ketamine infusion was associated with less short-term symptom improvement the following day. Furthermore, lower baseline LZC_T in the occipital region was identified as a potential predictive biomarker for a favorable response to ketamine, suggesting that individuals with initial lower complexity might benefit more from ketamine's neuroplastic effects.

4.1. Rapid ketamine effects on LZC during infusion

Our findings reveal significant insights into how subanesthetic doses of ketamine modulate EEG signal complexity. Specifically, enhancements in the richness and variability of patterns across EEG channels, quantified by LZC_T, reflect heightened neuronal activity (Hernández et al., 2023; Lempel and Ziv, 1976). This aligns with ketamine's mechanisms involving neuroplasticity and glutamatergic modulation, crucial for its rapid antidepressant effects (Price and Duman, 2020; Wang et al., 2022). The observed peak in LZC_T within 30 minutes of infusion corroborates findings from Murphy et al. (2023), who reported similar increase in EEG complexity shortly after ketamine administration. Computational models by Khaleghi et al. (2023) further suggest that an increase in the proportion of excitatory neurons under ketamine leads to more complex brain dynamics. This is consistent with the broader literature indicating that ketamine induces increased brain signal complexity and enhanced gamma oscillations (Lijffijt et al., 2021; Newport et al., 2015; Schartner et al., 2017; Sos et al., 2013), further demonstrated by the elevation of EEG vigilance stage B1 (Ip et al., 2024, 2021a). This stage, characterized by low-voltage EEG with dominant beta activity and reduced alpha activity (Ip et al., 2024), signifies a shift towards lower vigilance stages, effectively helping patients navigate from high to low vigilance phases (Ip et al., 2024, 2021a). Furthermore, ketamine's induction of EEG changes

extends to increasing beta power and promoting fast oscillations, often observed in therapeutic contexts and experimental settings like status epilepticus (Machado et al., 2022). These modifications suggest a dissociative state of vigilance (Corssen & Domino, 1966; de la Salle et al., 2016; Haaf et al., 2023), where the interplay between enhanced beta power and the overall increase in LZC_T underscores the complex influence of ketamine on brain activity.

Ketamine's ability to enhance EEG signal complexity was observed across all patients with MDD, irrespective of their response to treatment. This general enhancement indicates that ketamine consistently affects neuroplasticity and neural dynamics (Aleksandrova and Phillips, 2021; Kopelman et al., 2023; Price and Duman, 2020; Wang et al., 2022), highlighting its broad modulatory impact on brain activity in a clinical population. However, a greater increase in signal complexity during the second ketamine infusion, indicative of an enhanced excitatory/inhibitory ratio, was associated with less symptom improvement on the following day (Khaleghi et al., 2023). This indicates that although ketamine enhances EEG complexity, excessive increases might not contribute to clinical improvement (Duman et al., 2019; Milak et al., 2016; Möhler, 2012; Prévot and Sibille, 2021). Additionally, research shows that successful long-term mirtazapine treatment often normalizes EEG complexity to levels seen in healthy individuals, suggesting that therapeutic success may be associated with the stabilization of brain activity rather than a simple increase in complexity (Méndez et al., 2012).

Our results did not show significant regional differences in complexity changes during ketamine infusion, suggesting a more uniform effect across the brain. However, this finding contrasts with other studies that identified significant regional increases in signal complexity in the occipital and parietal regions, which are crucial for visual processing and sensory integration (Schartner et al., 2017; Song et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022). While we did not detect changes in LZC 24 hours

post-infusion, studies have documented neuroplasticity enhancements and connectivity changes in frontal lobe after this time (Abdallah et al., 2017; Kopelman et al., 2023). This suggests that the observed increase in regional neuronal connectivity and plasticity may not be captured by LZC changes. This suggests that our measurements might not align with the critical periods of synaptogenesis, which are proposed to peak 24-48 hours post-treatment (Moda-Sava et al., 2019; Muscat et al., 2021).

4.2. Pretreatment LZC as predictive biomarker for treatment response

Our study underscores the potential of using lower baseline occipital LZC_T as a predictive biomarker for positive responses to ketamine in patients with MDD. This finding aligns with earlier evidence suggesting that enhanced LZC in the occipital and parietal lobes—areas active during psychedelic experiences—is associated with vivid imagery and ego dissolution, which are crucial to ketamine’s antidepressant effects (Farnes et al., 2020; Schartner et al., 2017).

Further studies suggest that individuals with lower occipital complexity may experience more intense visual effects during ketamine, potential enhancing its therapeutic impact (Grundy et al., 2017; Sos et al., 2013). From the perspective of inhibition and excitatory balance (Khaleghi et al., 2023), patients with inherently lower complexity, benefit from ketamine intervention may derive greater benefits from ketamine’s ability to modulate GABAergic interneurons.

Furthermore, our recent findings also indicate that responders to ketamine typically start with a higher vigilance state and may achieve a lower vigilance state more rapidly (Ip et al., 2024). To further optimize treatment efficiency, practical strategies might include facilitating relaxation with pre-selected music, employing cognitive training with visual tasks to adjust occipital signal complexity, or encouraging patients to keep their eyes closed during infusion to reduce sensory input (Ibáñez-Molina et al., 2015; Muscat et al., 2021; Song et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2018).

These approaches aim to modulate the occipital region's signal complexity, potentially lowering it to maximize the therapeutic effects of ketamine by adjusting the excitation-inhibition balance in favor of treatment efficacy.

4.3. Association between LZC and clinical depressive scores

While no direct correlation was found between pretreatment LZC_T values and symptom severity across all patients, distinct patterns emerged when analyzing responders and non-responders to ketamine. Responders demonstrated a positive correlation between LZC_T in all regions except for the parietal area and symptom improvement the following day. Conversely, non-responders exhibited a positive correlation between frontal LZC_T and symptom severity, supporting literature that emphasizes the role of prefrontal and frontal complexities in depression (Čukić et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020). This pattern suggests that increased signal complexity in these regions might contribute to the persistence of symptoms, potentially impeding the therapeutic response to ketamine. These nuanced findings underscore the potential of LZC_T to help delineate clinical subtypes within TRD and suggest that different neural patterns may indicate underlying pathophysiological differences that influence treatment responsiveness.

Our study has several limitations. First, it focused exclusively on patients with moderate to severe depression, excluding individuals with mild depression or those experiencing suicidal ideation, which constrains the broader applicability of our findings. Moreover, the small sample size may compromise the statistical power and robustness of our conclusions. Lastly, the use of a low-density EEG cap has restricted our spatial resolution, potentially overlooking important neural dynamics that could be obtained with a high-density EEG setup.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms that subanesthetic doses of ketamine significantly enhance EEG signal complexity in treatment-resistant depression, reflecting heightened neuroplasticity and neuronal dynamism. Crucially, lower baseline occipital LZC_T serves as a promising predicting treatment outcome for favorable ketamine response, emphasizing its potential in treatment personalization. These insights into EEG complexity not only deepen our understanding of ketamine's mechanisms but also suggest a path forward for stratifying therapeutic approaches in major depressive disorder, potentially enhancing treatment efficacy and patient outcomes.

Funding

Collection of the data included in the study were supported by Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic (NV18-04-00260) and by the Charles University research program Cooperatio-Neurosciences. MB was supported by the Czech Science Foundation grant 21-32608S, and the ERDF-Project Brain Dynamics, No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004643. CTI was supported by the University of Macau (File no: SRG2023-00040-ICI and MYRG-GRG2024-00022-ICI). HZ is supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (32200845), the Science and Technology Development Fund, Macao S.A.R (FDCT, 0153/2022/A).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Weng-Lam Chan: Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization; **Sebastian Olbrich:** Writing – review & editing; **Xinwen Jiang:** Formal analysis;

Haoyun Zhang: Formal analysis; **Cheng-Teng Ip:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing; **Martin Brunovsky:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

SO and MB are co-founders and shareholders at DeepPsy AG. CTI is a shareholder of DeepPsy AG. All other authors declare no competing interests.

Acknowledgments

We thank all patients for taking part in this study. We thank all investigators involved in the study.

References

- Aamodt, A., Sevenius Nilsen, A., Markhus, R., Kusztor, A., HasanzadehMoghadam, F., Kauppi, N., Thürer, B., Storm, J.F., Juel, B.E., 2023. EEG Lempel-Ziv complexity varies with sleep stage, but does not seem to track dream experience. *Front Hum Neurosci* 16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2022.987714>
- Abdallah, C.G., Jackowski, A., Salas, R., Gupta, S., Sato, J.R., Mao, X., Coplan, J.D., Shungu, Di.C., Mathew, S.J., 2017. The Nucleus Accumbens and Ketamine Treatment in Major Depressive Disorder. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 42, 1739–1746. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2017.49>
- Abdallah, C.G., Sanacora, G., Duman, R.S., Krystal, J.H., 2018. The neurobiology of depression, ketamine and rapid-acting antidepressants: Is it glutamate inhibition or activation? *Pharmacol Ther.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pharmthera.2018.05.010>
- Aboy, M., Hornero, R., Abásolo, D., Álvarez, D., 2006. Interpretation of the Lempel-Ziv complexity measure in the context of biomedical signal analysis. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 53, 2282–2288. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2006.883696>

- Aleksandrova, L.R., Phillips, A.G., 2021. Neuroplasticity as a convergent mechanism of ketamine and classical psychedelics. *Trends Pharmacol Sci*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tips.2021.08.003>
- Arns, M., Gordon, E., Boutros, N.N., 2017. EEG Abnormalities Are Associated with Poorer Depressive Symptom Outcomes with Escitalopram and Venlafaxine-XR, but Not Sertraline. *Clin EEG Neurosci* 48, 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550059415621435>
- Bachmann, M., Kalev, K., Suhhova, A., Lass, J., Hinrikus, H., 2015. Lempel Ziv complexity of EEG in depression, in: *IFMBE Proceedings*. Springer Verlag, pp. 58–61.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-11128-5_15
- Casali, A.G., Gosseries, O., Rosanova, M., Boly, M., Sarasso, S., Casali, K.R., Casarotto, S., Bruno, M.-A., Laureys, S., Tononi, G., Massimini, M., 2013. A Theoretically Based Index of Consciousness Independent of Sensory Processing and Behavior. *Sci Transl Med* 5, 198ra105.
- Čukić, M., Stokić, M., Radenković, S., Ljubisavljević, M., Simić, S., Savić, D., 2020. Nonlinear analysis of EEG complexity in episode and remission phase of recurrent depression. *Int J Methods Psychiatr Res* 29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mpr.1816>
- Deyama, S., Kaneda, K., 2023. Role of neurotrophic and growth factors in the rapid and sustained antidepressant actions of ketamine. *Neuropharmacology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2022.109335>
- Duman, R.S., Sanacora, G., Krystal, J.H., 2019. Altered Connectivity in Depression: GABA and Glutamate Neurotransmitter Deficits and Reversal by Novel Treatments. *Neuron*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.03.013>
- Farnes, N., Juel, B.E., Nilsen, A.S., Romundstad, L.G., Storm, J.F., 2020. Increased signal diversity/complexity of spontaneous EEG, but not evoked EEG responses, in ketamine-induced psychedelic state in humans. *PLoS One* 15.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0242056>
- Fitzgerald, P.B., Srithiran, A., Benitez, J., Daskalakis, Z.Z., Oxley, T.J., Kulkarni, J., Egan, G.F., 2008. An fMRI study of prefrontal brain activation during multiple tasks in patients with major depressive disorder. *Hum Brain Mapp* 29, 490–501.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.20414>
- Gonda, X., Dome, P., Neill, J.C., Tarazi, F.I., 2023. Novel antidepressant drugs: Beyond monoamine targets. *CNS Spectr*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1092852921000791>
- Grundy, J.G., Anderson, J.A.E., Bialystok, E., 2017. Bilinguals have more complex EEG brain signals in occipital regions than monolinguals. *Neuroimage* 159, 280–288.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2017.07.063>
- Hernández, M., Ponce-Meza, J., Saavedra-López, M., Campos Ugaz, W., Chanduvi, R., Monteza, W., 2023. Brain Complexity and Psychiatric Disorders, *Iran J Psychiatry*.
- Ibáñez-Molina, A.J., Iglesias-Parro, S., Soriano, M.F., Aznarte, J.I., 2015. Multiscale Lempel-Ziv complexity for EEG measures. *Clinical Neurophysiology* 126, 541–548.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2014.07.012>
- Ionescu, D.F., Rosenbaum, J.F., Alpert, J.E., 2015. Pharmacological approaches to the challenge of treatment-resistant depression. *Dialogues Clin Neurosci* 17, 111–126.
<https://doi.org/10.31887/dcns.2015.17.2/dionescu>
- Ip, C.T., de Bardeci, M., Kronenberg, G., Pinborg, L.H., Seifritz, E., Brunovsky, M., Olbrich, S., 2024. EEG-vigilance regulation is associated with and predicts ketamine response in major depressive disorder. *Transl Psychiatry* 14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02761-x>

- Ip, C.T., Ganz, M., Dam, V.H., Ozenne, B., Rüesch, A., Köhler-Forsberg, K., Jørgensen, M.B., Frokjaer, V.G., Søgaard, B., Christensen, S.R., Knudsen, G.M., Olbrich, S., 2021a. NeuroPharm study: EEG wakefulness regulation as a biomarker in MDD. *J Psychiatr Res* 141, 57–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2021.06.021>
- Ip, C.T., Olbrich, S., Ganz, M., Ozenne, B., Köhler-Forsberg, K., Dam, V.H., Beniczky, S., Jørgensen, M.B., Frokjaer, V.G., Søgaard, B., Christensen, S.R., Knudsen, G.M., 2021b. Pretreatment qEEG biomarkers for predicting pharmacological treatment outcome in major depressive disorder: Independent validation from the NeuroPharm study. *European Neuropsychopharmacology* 49, 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroneuro.2021.03.024>
- Khaleghi, A., Mohammadi, M.R., Shahi, K., Nasrabadi, A.M., 2023. Possible Neuropathological Mechanisms Underlying the Increased Complexity of Brain Electrical Activity in Schizophrenia: A Computational Study. *Iran J Psychiatry*.
- Kopelman, J., Keller, T.A., Panny, B., Griffio, A., Degutis, M., Spotts, C., Cruz, N., Bell, E., Do-Nguyen, K., Wallace, M.L., Mathew, S.J., Howland, R.H., Price, R.B., 2023. Rapid neuroplasticity changes and response to intravenous ketamine: a randomized controlled trial in treatment-resistant depression. *Transl Psychiatry* 13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-023-02451-0>
- Krystal, J.H., Sanacora, G., Duman, R.S., 2013. Rapid-acting glutamatergic antidepressants: The path to ketamine and beyond. *Biol Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopsych.2013.03.026>
- Lempel, A., Ziv, J., 1976. On the complexity of finite sequences. *IEEE Trans Inf Theory* 22, 75–81.
- Li, D., Mashour, G.A., 2019. Cortical dynamics during psychedelic and anesthetized states induced by ketamine. *Neuroimage* 196, 32–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2019.03.076>
- Lijffijt, M., Murphy, N., Iqbal, S., Green, C.E., Iqbal, T., Chang, L.C., Haile, C.N., Hirsch, L.C., Ramakrishnan, N., Fall, D.A., Swann, A.C., Al Jurdi, R.K., Mathew, S.J., 2021. Identification of an optimal dose of intravenous ketamine for late-life treatment-resistant depression: a Bayesian adaptive randomization trial. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 47, 1088–1095. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-021-01242-9>
- López-Solà, C., Subirà, M., Serra-Blasco, M., Vicent-Gil, M., Navarra-Ventura, G., Aguilar, E., Acebillo, S., Palao, D.J., Cardoner, N., 2020. Is cognitive dysfunction involved in difficult-to-treat depression? Characterizing resistance from a cognitive perspective. *European Psychiatry* 63. <https://doi.org/10.1192/j.eurpsy.2020.65>
- Lord, B., Allen, J.J.B., 2023. Evaluating EEG complexity metrics as biomarkers for depression. *Psychophysiology* 60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/psyp.14274>
- Marcantoni, W.S., Akoumba, B.S., Wassef, M., Mayrand, J., Lai, H., Richard-Devantoy, S., Beauchamp, S., 2020. A systematic review and meta-analysis of the efficacy of intravenous ketamine infusion for treatment resistant depression: January 2009 – January 2019. *J Affect Disord*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.09.007>
- McIntyre, R.S., Alsuwaidan, M., Baune, B.T., Berk, M., Demyttenaere, K., Goldberg, J.F., Gorwood, P., Ho, R., Kasper, S., Kennedy, S.H., Ly-Uson, J., Mansur, R.B., McAllister-Williams, R.H., Murrugh, J.W., Nemeroff, C.B., Nierenberg, A.A., Rosenblat, J.D., Sanacora, G., Schatzberg, A.F., Shelton, R., Stahl, S.M., Trivedi, M.H., Vieta, E., Vinberg, M., Williams, N., Young, A.H., Maj, M., 2023. Treatment-resistant depression: definition,

- prevalence, detection, management, and investigational interventions. *World Psychiatry* 22, 394–412. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.21120>
- McIntyre, R.S., Carvalho, I.P., Lui, L.M.W., Majeed, A., Masand, P.S., Gill, H., Rodrigues, N.B., Lipsitz, O., Coles, A.C., Lee, Y., Tamura, J.K., Iacobucci, M., Phan, L., Nasri, F., Singhal, N., Wong, E.R., Subramaniapillai, M., Mansur, R., Ho, R., Lam, R.W., Rosenblat, J.D., 2020. The effect of intravenous, intranasal, and oral ketamine in mood disorders: A meta-analysis. *J Affect Disord.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.06.050>
- Méndez, M.A., Zuluaga, P., Hornero, R., Gómez, C., Escudero, J., Rodríguez-Palancas, A., Ortiz, T., Fernández, A., 2012. Complexity analysis of spontaneous brain activity: Effects of depression and antidepressant treatment. *Journal of Psychopharmacology* 26, 636–643. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881111408966>
- Meyer, T., Brunovsky, M., Horacek, J., Novak, T., Andrashko, V., Seifritz, E., Olbrich, S., 2021. Predictive value of heart rate in treatment of major depression with ketamine in two controlled trials. *Clinical Neurophysiology* 132, 1339–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2021.01.030>
- Milak, M.S., Proper, C.J., Mulhern, S.T., Parter, A.L., Kegeles, L.S., Ogden, R.T., Mao, X., Rodriguez, C.I., Oquendo, M.A., Suckow, R.F., Cooper, T.B., Keilp, J.G., Shungu, D.C., Mann, J.J., 2016. A pilot in vivo proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy study of amino acid neurotransmitter response to ketamine treatment of major depressive disorder. *Mol Psychiatry* 21, 320–327. <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2015.83>
- Moda-Sava, R.N., Murdock, M.H., Parekh, P.K., Fetcho, R.N., Huang, B.S., Huynh, T.N., Witztum, J., Shaver, D.C., Rosenthal, D.L., Alway, E.J., Lopez, K., Meng, Y., Nellissen, L., Grosenick, L., Milner, T.A., Deisseroth, K., Bito, H., Kasai, H., Liston, C., 2019. Sustained rescue of prefrontal circuit dysfunction by antidepressant-induced spine formation. *Science* (1979) 364. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat8078>
- Mohammadi, Y., Moradi, M.H., 2021. Prediction of Depression Severity Scores Based on Functional Connectivity and Complexity of the EEG Signal. *Clin EEG Neurosci* 52, 52–60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550059420965431>
- Möhler, H., 2012. The GABA system in anxiety and depression and its therapeutic potential, in: *Neuropharmacology*. pp. 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2011.08.040>
- Murphy, N., Tamman, A.J.F., Lijffijt, M., Amarneh, D., Iqbal, S., Swann, A., Averill, L.A., O'Brien, B., Mathew, S.J., 2023. Neural complexity EEG biomarkers of rapid and post-rapid ketamine effects in late-life treatment-resistant depression: a randomized control trial. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 48, 1586–1593. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-023-01586-4>
- Muscat, S.A., Hartelius, G., Crouch, C.R., Morin, K.W., 2021. An Integrative Approach to Ketamine Therapy May Enhance Multiple Dimensions of Efficacy: Improving Therapeutic Outcomes With Treatment Resistant Depression. *Front Psychiatry* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.710338>
- Newport, D.J., Carpenter, L.L., McDonald, W.M., Potash, J.B., Tohen, M., Nemeroff, C.B., 2015. Ketamine and other NMDA antagonists: Early clinical trials and possible mechanisms in depression. *American Journal of Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2015.15040465>
- Nugent, A.C., Ballard, E.D., Gould, T.D., Park, L.T., Moaddel, R., Brutsche, N.E., Zarate, C.A., 2019. Ketamine has distinct electrophysiological and behavioral effects in depressed and healthy subjects. *Mol Psychiatry* 24, 1040–1052. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-018-0028-2>

- Perrin, F., Pernier, J., Bertrand, O., Giard, M.H., Echallier, J.F., 1987. Mapping of scalp potentials by surface spline interpolation. *Electroencephalogr Clin Neurophysiol* 66, 75–81.
- Prévot, T., Sibille, E., 2021. Altered GABA-mediated information processing and cognitive dysfunctions in depression and other brain disorders. *Mol Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-020-0727-3>
- Price, R.B., Duman, R., 2020. Neuroplasticity in cognitive and psychological mechanisms of depression: an integrative model. *Mol Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-019-0615-x>
- Rengasamy, M., Mathew, S., Howland, R., Griffo, A., Panny, B., Price, R., 2024. Neural connectivity moderators and mechanisms of ketamine treatment among treatment-resistant depressed patients: a randomized controlled trial. *EBioMedicine* 99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104902>
- Salvadore, G., Cornwell, B.R., Sambataro, F., Latov, D., Colon-Rosario, V., Carver, F., Holroyd, T., Diazgranados, N., MacHado-Vieira, R., Grillon, C., Drevets, W.C., Zarate, C.A., 2010. Anterior cingulate desynchronization and functional connectivity with the amygdala during a working memory task predict rapid antidepressant response to ketamine. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 35, 1415–1422. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npp.2010.24>
- Schartner, M.M., Carhart-Harris, R.L., Barrett, A.B., Seth, A.K., Muthukumaraswamy, S.D., 2017. Increased spontaneous MEG signal diversity for psychoactive doses of ketamine, LSD and psilocybin. *Sci Rep* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep46421>
- Song, X.M., Hu, X.W., Li, Z., Gao, Y., Ju, X., Liu, D.Y., Wang, Q.N., Xue, C., Cai, Y.C., Bai, R., Tan, Z.L., Northoff, G., 2021. Reduction of higher-order occipital GABA and impaired visual perception in acute major depressive disorder. *Mol Psychiatry* 26, 6747–6755. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41380-021-01090-5>
- Sos, P., Klirova, M., Novak, T., Kohutova, B., Horacek, J., Palenicek, T., 2013. Relationship of ketamine's antidepressant and psychotomimetic effects in unipolar depression. *Neuroendocrinology Letters* 34, 287–293.
- Vasavada, M.M., Leaver, A.M., Espinoza, R.T., Joshi, S.H., Njau, S.N., Woods, R.P., Narr, K.L., 2016. Structural connectivity and response to ketamine therapy in major depression: A preliminary study. *J Affect Disord* 190, 836–841. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2015.11.018>
- Wang, Y.T., Zhang, N.N., Liu, L.J., Jiang, H., Hu, D., Wang, Z.Z., Chen, N.H., Zhang, Y., 2022. Glutamatergic receptor and neuroplasticity in depression: Implications for ketamine and rapastinel as the rapid-acting antidepressants. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2022.01.024>
- Xue, S., Wang, S., Kong, X., Qiu, J., 2017. Abnormal Neural Basis of Emotional Conflict Control in Treatment-Resistant Depression: An Event-Related Potential Study. *Clin EEG Neurosci* 48, 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550059416631658>
- Zhang, X., Hu, Bin, Zhou, L., Moore, P., Chen, J., 2013. An EEG Based Pervasive Depression Detection for Females, in: Zu, Q., Hu, Bo, Elçi, A. (Eds.), *Pervasive Computing and the Networked World*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 848–861.
- Zhang, Y., Wang, C., Sun, C., Zhang, X., Wang, Y., Qi, H., He, F., Zhao, X., Wan, B., Du, J., Ming, D., 2015. Neural complexity in patients with poststroke depression: A resting EEG study. *J Affect Disord* 188, 310–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2015.09.017>
- Zhao, L., Yang, L., Li, B., Su, Z., Liu, C., 2020. Frontal Alpha Complexity of Different Severity Depression Patients. *J Healthc Eng* 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8854725>

- Zhou, W., Wang, N., Yang, C., Li, X.M., Zhou, Z.Q., Yang, J.J., 2014. Ketamine-induced antidepressant effects are associated with AMPA receptors-mediated upregulation of mTOR and BDNF in rat hippocampus and prefrontal cortex. *European Psychiatry* 29, 419–423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2013.10.005>
- Zhou, Y., Wang, C., Lan, X., Zheng, W., Li, H., Chao, Z., McIntyre, R.S., Ning, Y., 2022. The effectiveness of repeated intravenous ketamine on subjective and objective psychosocial function in patients with treatment-resistant depression and suicidal ideation. *J Affect Disord* 304, 78–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2022.02.032>
- Zhou, Y., Zheng, W., Liu, W., Wang, C., Zhan, Y., Li, H., Chen, L., Li, M., Ning, Y., 2018. Neurocognitive effects of six ketamine infusions and the association with antidepressant response in patients with unipolar and bipolar depression. *Journal of Psychopharmacology* 32, 1118–1126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0269881118798614>

Tables

Table 1. Demographics characteristics and comparisons for ketamine and placebo intervention

	Ketamine (n=24)	Placebo (n=24)			
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	<i>F-value</i>	95% CI	<i>p-value</i>
Demographics					
Sex (% male/female)	7/17 (29%/71%)		/	/	/
Age	43.67 (12.46)		/	/	/
Clinical: MADRS					
Pretreatment MADRS	27.33 (0.97)	27.50 (0.96)	1.34	[-0.05, 1.72]	0.26
Response (% R/NR)	12/12 (50%/50%)	1/23 (4%/96%)	/	/	< 0.001
24h Δ MADRS (% changes from 24h to pretreatment)	21.15 (3.89)	-0.31 (3.10)	11.48	[10.69, 32.23]	0.003
EEG: LZC					
Pretreatment whole- brain LZC _T	0.41 (0.03)	0.43 (0.03)	4.28	[-0.07, 0.02]	0.052
Pretreatment whole- brain LZC _S	1.15 (0.12)	0.15 (0.13)	0.95	[-0.02, 0.03]	0.34

Ketamine induced a significantly greater improvement in MADRS scores 24 hours after infusion compared to placebo ($F(1,20) = 11.48$, $p = 0.003$). No significant differences were observed in demographic characteristics or pretreatment measures between the groups (p values > 0.052). *Note.* MADRS, Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale; LZC_T, temporospatial LZC; LZC_S, spatiotemporal LZC; R, responders; NR, non-responders. Responders were defined by at least a 33% improvement in depressive symptoms assessed by the MADRS score 24 hours after intervention.

Table 2. LZC_T values in association with MADRS scores

	LZC _T	MADRS	partial <i>r</i>	95% CI	<i>p-value</i>	<i>df</i>
Pretreatment	Whole- brain	Pretreatment	0.18	[-0.11, 0.44]	0.22	44
		24h	0.17	[-0.25, 0.54]	0.43	20
		4d	-0.07	[-0.46, 0.34]	0.75	20
		7d	0.20	[-0.22, 0.56]	0.35	20
		14d	0.14	[-0.31, 0.54]	0.56	17
Frontal	Pretreatment	0.19	[-0.10, 0.45]	0.19	44	
	24h	0.30	[-0.12, 0.63]	0.15	20	
Parietal	Pretreatment	0.18	[-0.11, 0.44]	0.21	44	

		24h	0.11	[-0.31, 0.49]	0.61	20
	Temporal	Pretreatment	0.13	[-0.16, 0.40]	0.38	44
		24h	0.12	[-0.30, 0.50]	0.58	20
	Occipital	Pretreatment	0.16	[-0.13, 0.42]	0.28	44
		24h	-0.10	[-0.48, 0.32]	0.65	20
<i>Responders Only (n=12)</i>						
	Whole-brain	Pretreatment	-0.30	[-0.63, 0.11]	0.15	20
		24h	0.69	[0.20, 0.91]	0.012	8
	Frontal	Pretreatment	-0.36	[-0.67, 0.05]	0.085	20
		24h	0.66	[0.13, 0.89]	0.021	8
	Parietal	Pretreatment	-0.28	[-0.61, 0.14]	0.19	20
		24h	0.57	[-0.006, 0.86]	0.053	8
	Temporal	Pretreatment	-0.25	[-0.60, 0.17]	0.24	20
		24h	0.73	[0.27, 0.92]	0.007	8
	Occipital	Pretreatment	-0.13	[-0.51, 0.29]	0.55	20
		24h	0.83	[0.49, 0.95]	< 0.001	8
<i>Non-Responders Only (n=12)</i>						
	Whole-brain	Pretreatment	0.38	[-0.03, 0.68]	0.068	20
		24h	-0.0009	[-0.57, 0.57]	>0.99	8
	Frontal	Pretreatment	0.41	[-0.004, 0.70]	0.049	20
		24h	0.11	[-0.50, 0.64]	0.74	8
	Parietal	Pretreatment	0.39	[-0.02, 0.69]	0.060	20
		24h	0.02	[-0.56, 0.59]	0.96	8
	Temporal	Pretreatment	0.28	[-0.14, 0.61]	0.19	20
		24h	-0.13	[-0.65, 0.48]	0.70	8
	Occipital	Pretreatment	0.34	[-0.08, 0.65]	0.11	20
		24h	-0.18	[-0.68, 0.44]	0.57	8
Start-pre	Whole-brain (changes)	Pretreatment	0.15	[-0.27, 0.52]	0.50	20
		24h	-0.31	[-0.63, 0.11]	0.15	20
		4d	-0.22	[-0.57, 0.20]	0.30	20
		7d	-0.22	[-0.57, 0.20]	0.31	20
		14d	-0.28	[-0.64, 0.17]	0.22	17
End-pre	Whole-brain (changes)	Pretreatment	0.09	[-0.33, 0.47]	0.69	20
		24h	-0.42	[-0.71, -0.03]	0.039	20
		4d	-0.24	[-0.59, 0.18]	0.25	20
		7d	-0.23	[-0.58, 0.19]	0.28	20
		14d	-0.20	[-0.58, 0.25]	0.38	17

Across all patients, a significant partial correlation was observed only between end-pre LZC_T and MADRS scores 24 hours post-ketamine. Among responders, higher pretreatment LZC_T (across all regions except parietal) was associated with greater symptom improvement 24 hours post-ketamine. In contrast, among non-responders, higher frontal pretreatment LZC_T was linked to greater symptom severity.

Note. *r*, correlation coefficients; *df*, degree of freedom. LZC_T values at start-pre and end-pre were determined by the percentage changes in LZC_T values at start-infusion and end-infusion respectively, compared to the pre-infusion values. MADRS scores at 24h, 4d, 7d, and 14d were

calculated as percentage improvements from the pretreatment scores following ketamine infusion at each respective timepoint.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Effects of ketamine and placebo on LZC_T. **A.** Topographic map of percentage changes of LZC_T at start-pre, end-pre and 24h-pre in ketamine and placebo infusion. **B.** Percentage changes of whole-brain LZC_T during infusion. Ketamine led to a greater LZC_T percentage change than placebo in all patients during infusion. Note. * $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Occipital LZC_T as an indicator of ketamine response. **A.** Pretreatment LZC_T by brain region in non-responders and responders. Before ketamine treatment, responders exhibited significantly lower LZC_T values in the occipital region compared to non-responders. **B.** The logistic regression analysis yielded an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.75. Note. * $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3. Whole-brain LZC_T at end-pre in association with MADRS scores measured at pretreatment and various timepoints post-ketamine. **A, B.** A negative partial correlation was observed only between whole-brain LZC_T changes at end-pre and changes in MADRS scores at 24 hours post-ketamine across all patients, with no significant correlations observed at other timepoints. Note. * $p < 0.05$. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

A Association between pretreatment frontal LZC_T and pretreatment MADRS scores

B Association between pretreatment occipital LZC_T and percentage changes of MADRS scores 24h post-ketamine

Figure 4. Pretreatment regional LZC_T in association with MADRS scores at pretreatment and 24 hours post-ketamine, in responders and non-responders, respectively. A. A positive partial correlation was observed between pretreatment frontal LZC_T and pretreatment MADRS scores in non-responders. **B.** In responders, a positive partial correlation was observed between pretreatment whole-brain, frontal, temporal and occipital LZC_T and MADRS scores changes 24 hours post-ketamine.

Note. * $p < 0.05$.